

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING SETS IN ELEMENTARY MATHEMATICS LESSONS

Ergasheva B.

1st-year master's degree student of Angren University

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Abstract. *Familiarization with sets and operations on them is important for further study of many issues of the school curriculum on mathematics and at the same time promotes intensive development of mental operations and speech of students: children must constantly compare objects, identify similarities and differences in them, classify, build generalizations, express in speech and justify observed properties and relationships.*

The study of sets is prepared by studying the properties of sets of objects and operations with them in the 1st grade. This material is repeated here at a new, higher level.

Keywords: *introduction to sets and operations on them, questions of the school program in mathematics, development of mental operations and speech, students, properties and relations of a set.*

The transition to school age is associated with decisive changes in activities, communication, relationships with other people. Thinking and learning become the leading activities, the way of life changes, new responsibilities appear, and the child's relationships with others become new.

A child who enters school automatically takes a completely new place in the system of human relationships: he has permanent responsibilities related to educational activities. Close adults, a teacher, even strangers communicate with the child not only as a unique person, but also as a person who has taken on the obligation (it does not matter - voluntarily or under duress) to study, like all children of his age.

There is a transition from visual-figurative to verbal-logical thinking. The child develops logically correct reasoning: he uses operations. However, these are not yet formal - logical operations, the younger schoolchild cannot reason in a hypothetical plane. The operations characteristic of this age, J. Piaget called concrete, since they can be applied only to specific, visual material. In the process of learning, scientific concepts are formed in younger schoolchildren[3].

Having an extremely important influence on the development of verbal and logical thinking, they, nevertheless, do not arise out of nowhere. In order to learn them, children must have sufficiently developed everyday concepts - ideas acquired in preschool age and continuing to spontaneously appear outside the walls of school based on each child's own experience. Everyday concepts are the lower conceptual level, scientific ones are the upper, highest, distinguished by awareness and arbitrariness. According to L. S. Vygotsky, "everyday concepts grow upward through scientific ones, scientific concepts grow downward through everyday ones." Mastering the logic of science, a child establishes relationships between concepts, understands the content of generalized concepts, and this content, connecting with the child's everyday experience, as if absorbs it. A scientific concept in the process of assimilation goes from generalization to specific objects[2].

Mastering a system of scientific concepts in the learning process makes it possible to talk about the development of the basics of conceptual, or theoretical, thinking in primary school students. This thinking allows the student to solve problems, focusing not on external, visual signs and connections of objects, but on internal, essential properties and relationships. The development of theoretical thinking depends on the type of learning.

Along with mastering the content of the system of scientific concepts, the child masters the methods of organizing a new type of work for him - educational. At this moment, a qualitatively new property of the human psyche appears - reflection. It manifests itself in the ability to highlight the features of one's actions and make them the subject of analysis. Already by the fourth grade, the child can set an educational task for himself, draw up a work schedule, evaluate and check it[5].

As V. A. Sukhomlinsky said: "Learning becomes work only if it has the most important characteristics of any work - purpose, efforts, results." And then the result of educational work is scientific thinking. The development of other mental functions depends on the development of thinking. At the beginning of primary school age, perception is not differentiated enough. Because of this, the child sometimes confuses letters and numbers that are similar in writing. Although he can purposefully examine objects and drawings, he highlights the most striking, eye-catching properties, just like in preschool age - mainly color, shape, size[8].

By the end of primary school age, with appropriate training, synthesizing perception appears. Developing intelligence creates the ability to establish connections between elements of the perceived. Despite the fact that during this period, visual - figurative thinking, directly perceived by the child, is of great importance, no longer prevents him from reasoning and making correct conclusions. As is known, at 7 - 8 years old, Piaget's phenomena disappear. And now intellectual operations allow the child to judge things without strict dependence on the visual situation.

Memory develops in two directions - arbitrariness and meaningfulness. Younger schoolchildren are able to purposefully and arbitrarily memorize material that is not interesting to them. Younger schoolchildren have a good mechanical memory. They tend to reproduce verbatim what they have memorized. Improving semantic memory at this age makes it possible to master a fairly wide range of mnemonic techniques, i.e. rational ways of memorization. When a child comprehends educational material, understands it, he simultaneously memorizes it. Thus, intellectual work is at the same time a mnemonic activity, thinking and semantic memory are inextricably linked[7].

When primary school students study the concept of a set, certain difficulties arise. For example, it is difficult for children to understand what equal sets are. This leads to difficulties in understanding the meaning of such operations as union and intersection of sets, and these difficulties are present not only in schoolchildren, but even in students. The source of these difficulties lies in the confusion of two fundamental concepts - identical and the same.

Let us cite definitions from the textbook by L. G. Peterson: "Two sets are equal if they consist of the same elements. If sets A and B are equal, then we write $A = B$. The path is $A = \{\text{raspberry, strawberry, currant}\}$, $B = \{\text{strawberry, raspberry, currant}\}$. $A = B$ (they have the same elements, only in different orders)." After such an explanation, a complication may arise in the lesson, which was reported to the authors by Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor A. L.

Chekin. As an example, let us consider Figure 1, which schematically depicts a cabinet with two shelves.

On the top shelf there are three jars of jam (for example, cherry, strawberry, wild strawberry). On the bottom shelf there are the same three jars, but in a different order. The set of the three top jars is designated A in the picture, and the set of the three bottom jars is designated B. The teacher asks the student: "Are the sets A and B equal?" The student answers: "Yes, they are equal" [14].

So, we are faced with a serious problem: how to explain to a student that sets A and B are not equal, if, looking at the lines underlined above from the definition of equal sets A and B, he will not notice any difference between the definition of equal sets and obviously, is that in the definition given above, the names of objects are listed in curly brackets, and the objects themselves (elements of the set) are implied. What are these implied objects?

In the case under consideration, these are concepts denoted by the corresponding words. At the same time, Fig. 1 does not contain the names of objects, but, on the contrary, the objects themselves. Thus, when working with sets, we have to deal with two different situations [18].

Situation 1. The curly brackets list the names of objects (elements of the set).

Situation 2. The figure contains the objects themselves (elements of the set).

Let's consider the features of each situation.

When analyzing situation 1, it is important to pay attention to two conditions.

Condition 1. The enumeration written in curly brackets should not include the elements themselves under any circumstances, but only their names.

Condition 2. It should be clear from the context which objects the names listed in curly brackets correspond to. Then misunderstandings related to the "problem of equal sets" will not arise.

From what has been said above it follows that we should agree, for example, with the following equalities of sets defined by enumeration: $\{I, II, III, IV, V\} = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$; $\{\text{strawberry, raspberry}\} = \{\text{RASPBERRY, STRAWBERRY}\}$.

At the same time, an enumeration similar to an image is unacceptable due to its ambiguity.

Of course, one can specifically agree that an animal is the name of some object (and not the object itself). However, it is better to avoid this and use known standard alphabets for the production of names.

During the analysis of situation 2, it is also important to pay attention to two conditions.

Condition 1. As is known, in the macro world there are no absolutely identical objects. This circumstance must be emphasized in every possible way, and not glossed over! If the jars of jam shown in Fig. 1 had at least the most insignificant individual characteristics, the student could not have made a mistake. Thus, the objects present in the picture must necessarily have individual characteristics. Compliance with this condition will eliminate confusion, in which two different sets are taken as equal.

Condition 2. Compliance with the agreement on the methods of multiple depiction of the same object (set of objects). The case when it is necessary to depict the same set twice (three times, four times...) remains to be analyzed. For example, to show in a drawing that a set of three jars of jam will not change (will remain equal to itself) if we swap two jars. This is not difficult to achieve, for example, in this way: by placing in the drawing a "live character rearranging the jars" [13].

The problems of introducing the concept of "equal sets" listed above are related to the distinction between the concepts of "similar" and "the same". If younger students work with cards that (unlike pictures on a textbook page) can be moved, then these problems usually disappear. Note in this regard that the above-mentioned "living character" cannot be "similar", it is necessarily "the same"[9].

If a child plays with a three-dimensional material object that he can touch and observe, then there is no confusion between the concepts of "similar" and "the same". (For example: this is the same ball that the child was playing with, or a similar ball, but not the same.) But if a student has to work not with the objects themselves, but with their images (on a page in a textbook, on a computer monitor), then, unless special precautions are taken, confusion is inevitable. Two situations arise: the same object is depicted twice, or two identical objects are depicted.

A.A. Stolyar in his book "Formation of Elementary Mathematical Concepts in Preschoolers" says that already in childhood a child accumulates knowledge about different subjects and objects. Already in the first - second year of life, a child plays with various objects, such as: balls, rings and so on. He sorts, folds - unfolds, groups of objects by shape, size, color. Children get acquainted with such a concept as a set from their own experience: a set of people, a set of animals in the zoo - all this is perceived by auditory, visual analyzers[15].

The child distinguishes where there is one and where there are several objects, how one set differs from another, compares sets by the number of elements. Children group sets. For example, from buttons of a large and small size, two sets can be obtained. A. A. Stolyar believes that the formation of the concept of "set" is successful with a visual-effective form of learning. Attention develops in primary school age. Without sufficient development of this mental function, the learning process is impossible[12]. Younger schoolchildren are already able to concentrate on uninteresting actions, but their involuntary attention still prevails. For them, external impressions are a strong distraction, it is difficult for them to concentrate on incomprehensible, complex material. At this age, attention has a number of shortcomings, such as:

- narrow attention (the child is not able to observe many objects at the same time, and his attention is completely absorbed by the few that occupy him at the moment);
- easily fatigued attention (the child cannot concentrate for a long time, especially on one and the same thing);
- wandering attention (it is difficult for a schoolchild to establish attention, to fix it confidently, firmly and correctly);
- passive attention (children's attention is not very capable of voluntary effort and needs frequent stimulation);
- specific attention (it is directed mainly to objects of external perception).

In educational activities, the child's voluntary attention develops. Initially following the teacher's instructions, working under his constant supervision, he gradually acquires the ability to complete tasks independently - he sets the goal himself and controls his actions. Control over the process of his activity is, in fact, the voluntary attention of the student.

Different children are attentive in different ways: attention has different properties, and these properties develop in them to different degrees, creating individual variations. Some students have stable attention, but poorly switchable attention, they solve one problem for a long time and diligently, but it is difficult for them to quickly move on to the next. Others easily switch during

the course of study, but are also easily distracted by extraneous matters. Still others have good attention organization combined with a small volume of attention[20].

In general, two main lines of development of mental functions can be distinguished - intellectualization and arbitrariness. We believe that the success of the formation of the concept of set in primary school students can be increased by using multimedia technologies in lessons.

Multimedia technologies are a set of modern means of audio, television, visual and virtual communications used in the process of organizing, planning and managing various types of activities. The use of ICT in a modern school is already more of a necessity than an additional means. Let us briefly consider which multimedia technologies can be used to form the concept of plurality in children.

Multimedia presentations are most often used in lessons. Using bright, colorful slides with added music or moving pictures, links and transitions, a teacher can attract children's attention even to boring concepts. By studying a new definition on a presentation slide rather than in a textbook, children remember it faster, their interest in the subject and desire to learn new things are activated. Presentations can be used to show drawings, graphs, tables, etc[10].

One of the most frequently used technical devices in lessons is an interactive whiteboard. The possibilities of an interactive whiteboard are practically unlimited, it allows you to show children any process in an interactive mode. When studying the concept of a set, students can clearly see the operations of intersection and union of sets on the interactive whiteboard. At the same time, the teacher has the ability to move, superimpose, delete or add new objects. The interactive whiteboard expands the presentation possibilities, as the teacher can emphasize the important during the slide show, highlight in color or in other ways what needs to be brought to the children's attention. When reinforcing a new concept, using the interactive whiteboard will allow children to see their mistakes and correct them immediately. Quality control of the assimilation of concepts is carried out using test templates, of which there are quite a lot in the software included with the board.

The ability to identify sets and give them names is only the initial stage in the formation of ideas about sets. Visual aids play an important role in the study of this material. The purpose of the visual aid method is to enrich and expand children's immediate, sensory experience, develop visual aids, study specific properties of objects, create conditions for the transition to abstract thinking, support for independent learning and systematization of what has been learned. Natural, pictorial, volumetric, sound and graphic visual aids are used[17].

Visual aids are varied: objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality, actions of the teacher and children, images of real objects, processes (drawings, pictures), models of objects (toys, cardboard cutouts), symbolic images (maps, tables, diagrams).

Visual methods are used at all stages of the pedagogical process.

Work related to observation, comparison of groups of objects should be carried out constantly. Visual aids and didactic materials should be widely used.

The geometrical method of conventionally denoting things and their relationships by drawing, sketch, etc. is a means of easier presentation and memorization of the studied material.

During the formative experiment, the following tasks were set and solved:

development of didactic games and presentations aimed at developing ideas about the set.

create a developmental environment;

determine the most optimal approach for children of primary school age.

The world of a child is very colorful and emotional. When coming to a lesson, you want the children to be interested, so that they learn the material well. For this purpose, we have developed lessons using multimedia presentations. PowerPoint presentation slides are a convenient and effective way to provide children with knowledge about the objects that surround them[19].

The presentation combines sound and colorful images, which significantly improves the perception of information. Showing a presentation can be compared to showing a beautiful children's book, where on all pages there is a large bright picture with a caption. All this helps children remember complex information more easily. One of the most important tasks of a teacher in light of the national curriculum is to teach a student to live in the information world. And here the question of the ICT competence of a teacher arises, i.e. knowledge of new information technologies and the ability to use them.

Experience has shown that the use of modern ICT technologies in lessons:

- activates the cognitive activity of students;
- increases the motivation of students to the subject being studied;
- saves time on explaining the material;
- allows you to go beyond school textbooks, supplement and deepen their content;
- allows you to differentiate and individualize the work of students;
- makes it possible to increase the cumulateness of grades;
- creates comfort in the classroom.

Activation of students' cognitive activity when using ICT is achieved due to:

- high illustrative and informational saturation in the lesson;
- differentiation of questions to the same task;
- selection of interesting material;
- higher pace of students' work.

That is why we used work with MacBooks, in particular, in the "PervoLogo" program. Such lessons are of interest to younger students.

At the formative stage, we conducted lessons using multimedia technologies, developed presentations to develop children's cognitive interest, as well as didactic games aimed at forming younger school-age children's ideas about the set.

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